

Handling of Indeterminacy in Statistics. Application in Community Medicine

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Abstract. Currently, humanity has made significant progress in the development of telecommunications and the economic, social, and health sectors; probably, in the same way, a series of pathogenic organisms have evolved considerably, causing harm to humanity. That is why Health Sciences has resorted to the technological advances offered by the industrial and telecommunications era. Among the tools of great help to combat infectious agents are statistical tools, which contribute a decisive step in advancing scientific studies aimed at communities and society. The application of Statistics in Health Sciences is essential to apply its knowledge in preventive activities, health promotion, and clinical studies. This knowledge allows students to face more complex courses and content and formulate better scientific criteria for analyzing and developing healthcare and research activities. Although a level of evidence has been achieved in the recommendations for tracking the health problems faced by the communities and the possible treatments to be applied in patients, there are still certain levels of indeterminacy in the analyzed data that generate arbitrary or discretionary opinions outside the scope of the classical statistics which can be better covered if processed by neutrosophic statistics.

Keywords: community medicine, neutrosophic statistics

1 Introduction

The great social changes of the last decades have allowed significant achievements in technological development, research, and the availability of information. The increasing volume and accelerated appearance of data have led to a decrease in their timing and validity and complicate the need for health professionals to be responsibly updated [1]. The doctor needs to have and adopt tools such as bibliographic search techniques and formal rules to evaluate the literature, which allows the selection and prioritization of the generous information that circulates and which helps to face the challenge of professional updating [2, 3].

The need for a statistical approach is now well recognized in research and practice in the disciplines that constitute health [4], subdivided into communities or populations in which the laws of large numbers and random fluctuations apply [5].

The analysis of the health situation is based on an exhaustive review of statistical data with a clinical-epidemiological and social approach to identify the problems of the individual, families, and the community [6], as well as its possible solutions [7] when developing the work of the health team [8]. As a teaching instrument, it is considered that the objective is for the student to get ahold of the procedure, actively, independently, consciously, and creatively, using the clinical-epidemiological and statistic method [9], and the planning of strategies with a cultural-historical and integral approach [10].

Statistical information makes use of personal and family medical records, vaccination cards, and the insertion of data of interest in clinical forms [11-14]. Subsequently, an integral analysis is made; the problems and their origin are identified; priorities and solutions are established to reduce risk and promote a healthy life; and finally, an action plan is drawn up with tasks and different activities that must solve the identified problems [15]. Each activity must have its completion date and the person responsible identified; the activities or tasks will be monitored and evaluated in a participatory way [16] so that responsibility is maintained while comparing the modifications with those of the analysis of the health situation that has preceded it [17]. All of the above must be reflected in a document and presented to the population so that the patient contributes with ideas and solutions to the identified problems [18].

The extent of statistical knowledge and skills that public health professionals need to acquire [17] area very important, because knowledge of statistical principles and methods and competence in their application is needed for the effective exercise of health in the community and society [19] [20], and additionally for the understanding and interpretation of the data [21]. This study is focused on analyzing one of the many variables that interact in the health field to achieve consensus between arbitrary or discretionary opinions, as indeterminate elements regarding the criteria evaluated in a scientific context [22], with the use of neutrosophic statistics [23] [24].

Based on the analysis referred to in the study and the level of indeterminacy in the neutrosophic statistical data, this study focuses on:

- Problem situation: differences in criteria when making a clinical decision in tracking the health problems faced by communities
- Main objective: determine the levels of evidence in the recommendations for tracking health problems in community medicine
- Specific objectives:
 - Determine the factors and degrees of recommendations for preventive practices by specialists in the clinical pictures presented.
 - Carry out the measurement and modeling of the neutrosophic variable
 - Present potential alternatives when evaluating the existing indeterminacies of the analyzed variable

Regarding the structuring of the study, the following is exposed:

Figure 1: Structure of the study.

2 Materials and methods

Neutrosophic statistics

[25-46] Neutrosophic probabilities and statistics are a generalization of classical and imprecise probabilities and statistics. The Neutrosophic Probability of an event E is the probability that event E will occur [47], the probability that event E does not occur, and the probability of indeterminacy (not knowing whether event E occurs or not). In classical probability $n_{sup} \leq 1$, while in neutrosophic probability $n_{sup} \leq 3$ +. The function that models the neutrosophic probability of a random variable x is called the neutrosophic distribution:

$$NP(x) = (T(x), I(x), F(x)),$$

Where T(x) represents the probability that the value x occurs, F(x) represents the probability that the value x does not occur, and I(x) represents the indeterminate or unknown probability of the value x.

Neutrosophic Statistics is the analysis of neutrosophic events and deals with neutrosophic numbers, the neutrosophic probability distribution [48], neutrosophic estimation, neutrosophic regression, etc. It refers to a set of data formed totally or partially by data with some degree of indeterminacy and the methods to analyze them.

Neutrosophic statistical methods allow the interpretation and organization of neutrosophic data (data that can be ambiguous, vague, imprecise, incomplete, or even unknown) to reveal the underlying patterns [49].

In short, the Neutrosophic Logic [50, 51], Neutrosophic Sets, and Neutrosophic Probabilities and Statistics have a wide application in various research fields and constitute a new reference of study in full development.

The Neutrosophic Descriptive Statistics includes all of the techniques to summarize and describe the characteristics of the neutrosophic numerical data [52].

Neutrosophic Numbers are numbers of the form $N = a + bI$ where a and b are real or complex numbers [53], while "I" is the indeterminacy part of the neutrosophic number N.

The study of neutrosophic statistics refers to a neutrosophic random variable where X_l and $X_u I_N$ represents the corresponding lower and upper level that the studied variable can reach, in an indeterminate interval $[I_l, I_u]$. Following the neutrosophic mean of the variable when formulating (\bar{x}_N) :

$$X_N = X_l + X_u I_N; I_N \in [I_l, I_u] \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Where, } \bar{x}_a = \frac{1}{n_N} \sum_{i=1}^{n_N} X_{il}, \bar{x}_b = \frac{1}{n_N} \sum_{i=1}^{n_N} X_{iu}, n_N \in [n_l, n_u] \tag{2}$$

is a neutrosophic random sample. However, for the calculation of neutral frames (NNS), it can be calculated as follows.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_N} (X_i - \bar{X}_{iN})^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{n_N} \left[\begin{matrix} \min \left((a_i + b_i I_L)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_L), (a_i + b_i I_U)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_U) \right) \\ \max \left((a_i + b_i I_L)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_L), (a_i + b_i I_U)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_U) \right) \end{matrix} \right], I \in [I_L, I_U] \quad (3)$$

Where $a_i = X_i b_i = X_U$. The variance of the neutrosophic sample can be calculated by

$$S_N^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_N} (X_i - \bar{X}_{iN})^2}{n_N}; S_N^2 \in [S_L^2, S_U^2] \quad (4)$$

The neutrosophic coefficient (NCV) measures the consistency of the variable. The lower the NCV value, the more consistent the factor's performance is than the other factors. For example, NCV can be calculated as follows[54].

$$CV_N = \frac{\sqrt{S_N^2}}{\bar{X}_N} \times 100; CV_N \in [CV_L, CV_U] \quad (5)$$

3 Results

Data collection

Statistics make it possible to analyze situations in which the sample includes random components that contribute significantly to the variability of the data obtained. In community health, the random components are due, among other aspects, to the knowledge or the impossibility of measuring some determinants of the health and disease statuses and the variability in the responses given by the patients who are subjected to the same treatment.

For the development of the neutrosophic statistical study, it is recommended by the experts to analyze the levels of evidence in the recommendations for tracking health problems from the statistical study bases in community medicine (Table 1).

Development of the method

For the neutrosophic statistical modeling of the clinical decision of the health specialist, five factors are selected equivalent to five clinical decisions that exist in the health field, based on typical conditions in the community and society (Table 2).

Variable	Coding	Sample by factor	Scale
Levels of evidence in the recommendations for tracking health problems in community medicine	ERPS	100	[0; 1], $\forall F_n$ ERPS = 0 (false) ERPS = 1 (True) ERPS \neq 0.5 (Existing indeterminacy in ERPS)

Table 1. Characteristics of the variable. Own elaboration

It should be taken into account that the recommendations are subject to constant updates motivated by advances in clinical research and the contributions of statistical information at the international level.

Factor	Clinical diagnosis of the patient	Grade	Recommendations of preventive practices by specialists	Scale	Range of acceptance of the clinical decision regarding treatment
F1	Hypertension screening in people over 18 years of age.	A	Intervention is recommended. Good evidence was found that the measure	[0; 1]	[0; 1], $\forall F_1$ ERPS = 0 (false)
F2	Breast cancer screening with mammography every	B	Intervention is recommended. Moderate evidence was found that the measure improves	[0; 1]	$0 \leq ERPS \leq 1$;

	1-2 years in women aged 40 and over.		health outcomes. The benefits outweigh the risks		ERPS = 1 (True)
F3	Routine screening for osteoporosis in postmenopausal women under 60 years of age.	C	There is no recommendation for or against the intervention. At least moderate evidence was found that the measure improves health outcomes. The benefits are very similar to the risks.	[0; 1]	ERPS ≠ 0.5 (Level of acceptance of the recommendation among specialists)
F4	Screening for pancreatic cancer in asymptomatic adults using abdominal palpation, ultrasound, or serological markers.	D	It is recommended against performing the intervention. We found moderate evidence that the measure is ineffective. The risks outweigh the benefits.	[0; 1]	ERPS = 0.5 (Indeterminacy of ERPS level, other clinical studies are required to make a consensual and accepted decision)
F5	Routine screening for dementia in the elderly	I	The evidence is insufficient to recommend for or against the intervention.	[0; 1]	

Table 2. Process of basing clinical decisions based on the definitive diagnosis of the patient. Own elaboration

For the development of the statistical study, the neutrosophic frequencies of the factors are analyzed to relate the consensus of clinical decisions based on the definitive diagnosis of the patient. For each factor, a clinical decision agreed by health specialists is analyzed before a definitive diagnosis of the patient in days that make up the set of clinical decisions regarding treatment in a group of patients (Table 3).

Days	Neutrosophic frequencies				
	A	B	C	D	I
1	[0.3; 1]	[0.2; 1]	[0.2; 1]	[0.3; 1]	[0.4; 1]
2	[1 ; 1]	[0.2; 1]	[0.2; 1]	[0.1; 1]	[0.9; 1]
3	[0.5; 1]	[0.9; 1]	[0.3; 1]	[0.7; 1]	[0.5; 1]
4	[0.8; 1]	[0; 1]	[0.5; 1]	[0.5; 1]	[1 ; 1]
5	[1 ; 1]	[0.1; 1]	[0.7; 1]	[0.8; 1]	[0; 1]
6	[0.6; 1]	[0; 1]	[0.4; 1]	[0.1; 1]	[0.8; 1]
7	[1 ; 1]	[0; 1]	[0.1; 1]	[0.2; 1]	[0.9; 1]
8	[0.8; 1]	[0.7; 1]	[0.3; 1]	[1 ; 1]	[0.6; 1]
9	[0.6; 1]	[1 ; 1]	[0.8; 1]	[0.1; 1]	[0.9; 1]
10	[0; 1]	[0.6; 1]	[0.5; 1]	[0; 1]	[0.5; 1]
11	[0.3; 1]	[0.8; 1]	[0.3; 1]	[0.4; 1]	[0.3; 1]
12	[0.1; 1]	[0.4; 1]	[0.8; 1]	[0.2; 1]	[0.5; 1]
13	[0.5; 1]	[0.8; 1]	[0.8; 1]	[0.5; 1]	[1 ; 1]
14	[0.1; 1]	[0.9; 1]	[0.4; 1]	[0.5; 1]	[0.2; 1]
15	[0.9; 1]	[0.9; 1]	[0; 1]	[0.9; 1]	[0.3; 1]
16	[0.5; 1]	[1 ; 1]	[0.8; 1]	[0.2; 1]	[0.5; 1]
17	[0.7; 1]	[0.3; 1]	[0.9; 1]	[0.6; 1]	[0.6; 1]
18	[1 ; 1]	[0.6; 1]	[0.1; 1]	[0.2; 1]	[0.1; 1]
19	[0; 1]	[1 ; 1]	[0.5; 1]	[0.4; 1]	[0.3; 1]
20	[0.4; 1]	[0.2; 1]	[0.5; 1]	[0.4; 1]	[0; 1]
0-100	[51.1; 100]	[49.9; 100]	[48.9; 100]	[50.4; 100]	[53.9; 100]

Table 3. Relative neutrosophic frequency of the ERPS level. Own elaboration

Table 3 analyzes the level of ERPS for a sample of 100 patients from the community for each factor, of which the level of acceptance of health specialists about the clinical decision regarding treatment is measured. From the neutrosophic frequencies, it can be observed with a level of acceptance of the clinical decision regarding the treatment of [0; 1] for each clinical picture reviewed with a level of total indeterminacy of $A = 48.9, B = 50.1, C = 51.1, D = 49.6, I = 46.1$, with a level of representativeness of [46.1%; 51,1%], on the days that

complex clinical pictures are evaluated. of patients, where the preliminary screening results have a level of contradiction or indeterminacy close to 0.5 per factor analyzed, with a higher incidence of factors *screening for breast cancer with mammography every 1-2 years in women over 40 years of age and screening for pancreatic cancer in asymptomatic adults using abdominal palpation, ultrasound or serological markers*. Given the existing levels of indeterminacy, the use of classical statistics is not appropriate, so it is necessary to use neutrosophic statistics for a better understanding.

Neutrosophic statistical analysis

While modeling the data on the level of acceptance of the clinical decision regarding the treatment of afflictions of the evaluated patients, it can be observed that factors 2 and 4 require studies with a level of depth to determine an accurate prognosis (Table 4). To understand which factor implies a representative mean, $\bar{x} = \in [\bar{x}_L; \bar{x}_U]$, the values of the neutrosophic means are calculated, and for the study of the variations of the afflictions, the values of the neutrosophic standard deviation $S_N \in [S_L; S_U]$. To determine which factor requires a level of evidence in the recommendations for tracking health problems in community medicine, the values $CV_N \in [CV_L; CV_U]$ are calculated.

Factors	\bar{x}_N	YN	CVN
Hypertension screening in people over 18 years of age.	0.852 + 1.667 I	0.157 + 0.808 I	0.184 + 0.485 I
Breast cancer screening with mammography every 1-2 years in women aged 40 and over.	0.832 + 1.667 I	0.16 + 0.811 I	0.192 + 0.487 I
Routine screening for osteoporosis in postmenopausal women under 60 years of age.	0.815 + 1.667 I	0.129 + 0.728 I	0.158 + 0.437 I
Screening for pancreatic cancer in asymptomatic adults using abdominal palpation, ultrasound, or serological markers.	0.84 + 1.667 I	0.107 + 0.704 I	0.127 + 0.422 I
Routine screening for dementia in the elderly	0.898 + 1.667 I	0.125 + 0.721 I	0.139 + 0.433 I

Table 4. Neutrosophic statistical analysis of the level of ERPS. Own elaboration

Table 4 shows that for the routine screening of dementia in the elderly, health specialists needed a level of clinical studies to achieve consensus in the clinical decision lower than the other factors analyzed. This means that the I degree recommendation for the corresponding type of clinical picture is, on average, the one that most influences when it comes to obtaining the consensus of the specialists without having to resort to the results of studies of great clinical complexity. On the other hand, the CV_{ND} analysis for this factor is lower compared to the rest. This represents that for the screening of pancreatic cancer in asymptomatic adults using abdominal palpation, ultrasound, or serological markers there is a level of contradiction and uncertainty when deciding a treatment if there are no weight elements to apply D degree recommendation with the necessary clinical tests (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Neutrosophic bar graph of ERPS incidents from clinical specialists. Own elaboration

Comparative analysis

To determine the associated indeterminacy measure $\bar{x} = \in [\bar{x}_L; \bar{x}_U]$, $S_N \in [S_L; S_U]$ and $CV_N \in [CV_L; CV_U]$ for the form of neutrosophic numbers (Table 5). In the results obtained, it is observed that the values go from 0.127 to 0.192 with the measure of indeterminacy of 69.9 generated by *screening for pancreatic cancer in asymptomatic adults using abdominal palpation, ultrasound, or serological markers*. It is required for these clinical pictures that more in-depth studies be directed for screening tracking of health problems in community medicine and the search for statistical studies on the subject where contradictions and indeterminacies are diversified in various degrees of recommendation to obtain a level of consensus of specialists within the analyzed element of the neutrosophic set of the community.

Factors	\bar{x}_N	YN	CVN
F1	0.852 + 1.667 I; I ∈ [0; 0.48]	0.157 + 0.808; I ∈ [0; 0.80]	0.184 + 0.485 I; I ∈ [0; 0.62]
F2	0.832 + 1.667 I; I ∈ [0; 0.50]	0.16 + 0.811 I; I ∈ [0; 0.80]	0.192 + 0.487 I; I ∈ [0; 0.60]
F3	0.815 + 1.667 I; I ∈ [0; 0.51]	0.129 + 0.728 I; I ∈ [0; 0.82]	0.158 + 0.437 I; I ∈ [0; 0.63]
F4	0.84 + 1.667 I; I ∈ [0; 0.49]	0.107 + 0.704 I; I ∈ [0; 0.84]	0.127 + 0.422 I; I ∈ [0; 0.69]
F5	0.898 + 1.667 I; I ∈ [0; 0.46]	0.125 + 0.721 I; I ∈ [0; 0.82]	0.139 + 0.433 I; I ∈ [0; 0.67]

Table 5. Neutrosophic forms with a measure of indeterminacy

The results obtained in the study propose promoting alternatives based on the results of preliminary clinical studies in patients with presented clinical pictures. The variants presented allow actions to be taken based on the level of indeterminacy and acceptance of the levels of evidence in the recommendations for tracking health problems in community medicine (Figure 3).

Partial solutions

Figure 3. Alternatives based on the neutrosophic states of the ERPS variable [0; 1]. Own elaboration

Conclusions

- Statistical analysis in medicine provides knowledge of the population's health status by considering the different indicators for the population, scientific contributions, and statistical studies of diagnoses of clinical pictures. Although, the scenario measures deviations from the health status and not the health itself, it must be taken into account that the community health situation may vary greatly in short periods and the learning of the elaboration of the analysis of the health situation has a formative character for the learners.
- Neutrosophic statistics reveal a more direct approach in community health, considering among the investigations the indeterminacies of the variables that influence the health field. This study made it possible to evaluate the levels of evidence in the recommendations for the screening of health problems in community medicine, among which the screening factor for *pancreatic cancer in asymptomatic adults using abdominal palpation, ultrasound, or serological markers* as an element with a CV of 69.9% of indeterminacy for the analyzed sample so that it affects the moment of giving a diagnosis and a correct grade of recommendation.
- Neutrosophic statistics are present in each health field dimension, subdivided into neutrosophic components of the analyzed variable. Each alternative responds to each neutrosophic state of the variable in the neutrosophic set. Statistical studies and research are required to determine variables with a level of indeterminacy in the field of study.

References

- [1] OMS, "Estadísticas sanitarias mundiales 2011," ed. Ginebra: OMS, 2011.
- [2] L. Á. Castaño. (2009) Los determinantes sociales de la salud: más allá de los factores de riesgo. *Gerenc. Polit. Salud.* 69-79.
- [3] C. d. l. O. M. d. l. Salud, "Glosario de promoción de la Salud," ed. Madrid 1999.
- [4] J. A. Orozco, *El análisis estadístico en medicina. COMPENDIUM* vol. 13, No. 2: Investigaciones Clínicas Latinoamericanas, 1993.
- [5] A. DG, *Practical statistics for medical research*. London: Chapman & Hall, 1991.
- [6] S. D. y. col, *Epidemiología clínica. Ciencia básica para la medicina clínica*, 1994.
- [7] I. E. d. S. Social. (2010). *Seguro de Salud*. Available: <http://www.iess.gov.ec/site.php?category=seguro-de-salud>
- [8] W. W. Daniel, *Bioestadística. Ed. .* Limusa Wiley 2002.
- [9] M. G. JA, *Atención Sanitaria – Basada en la Evidencia – Ed.* Churchill Livingstone, 1997.
- [10] L. P, *El peso de la enfermedad en las provincias del Ecuador*. Quito: CEPAR, 2000.
- [11] I. N. d. E. e. Informática, "Resultados de la Encuesta Demográfica y de Salud Familiar 2013," ed. Lima: Instituto Nacional de Estadística e Informática, 2013.
- [12] B.-M. J, *State of health of the Catalan Areas: the Work of the Acadèmia d'Higiene in the Early 20th Century. Health and medicine in rural Europe*. Valencia: Barona Vilar JL, Cherry S, 2005.
- [13] J. M. Macías Bermúdez, G. K. Arreaga Farias, and L. Torres Torres, "A Method for Decision-Making on the Tendering Procedure for the Acquisition of Goods and Services in Public Procurement," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 235-241, 2020.
- [14] O. J. A. Machado, T. T. Bastidas, and M. Y. L. Vázquez, "EXTRACCIÓN DE CONOCIMIENTO A PARTIR DEL ANÁLISIS DE LOS DATOS EN EL PERÍODO 2013-2017 DEL MINISTERIO DE SALUD PÚBLICA EN ECUADOR," *Investigación Operacional*, vol. 41, pp. 629-637, 2020.
- [15] I. N. d. E. y. Censos, "Indicadores básicos de salud. Ecuador 2009," ed. Quito: Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, 2009.
- [16] Rodríguez Ocaña E and B.-M. J, *El legítimo criterio estadístico. Los métodos cuantitativos en la salud pública española, 1800-1936. Epidemiología y estadística. V Encuentro Marcelino Pascua*. Granada: EASP, 1996.
- [17] M. d. C. d. D. Social, "Registros institucionales del IESS, ISSFA e ISSPOL," ed. Quito: Ministerio de Coordinación de Desarrollo Social, 2010.
- [18] A. E. Ortiz P, "Ecuador: estimaciones y proyecciones de población 1950-2025," ed Quito: Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, 2003.
- [19] C.-B. Cheng, *Control de proceso difuso: construcción de gráficos de control con números difusos*, *Conjuntos difusos Syst* vol. 154, no. 2, 2005.
- [20] J. H. Wang and T. RAZ. (1990) Sobre la construcción de gráficos de control utilizando variables lingüísticas", En t. *J. Prod. Res.* 477–487.
- [21] N. M. Downie and R. W. Heat, *Métodos estadísticos aplicados*: Harla, 1983.
- [22] S. Şentürk, N. Erginel, I. Kaya, and C. Kahraman. (2014) Gráfico de control de promedio móvil ponderado exponencialmente difuso para datos univariados con una aplicación de caso real", *Appl. Soft Comput.*
- [23] M.-H. Shu and H.-C. Wu. (2011) "Gráficos de control difusos X y R: enfoque de dominio difuso. . *Ind. Eng.* . 676–685.

- [24] M. Aslam and N. Khan, "Un nuevo gráfico de control de variables que utiliza el método de intervalo neutrosófico: una aplicación a la industria del automóvil," *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, vol. 36, no.3, 2019.
- [25] A. Romero Fernández, E. Labrada González, and D. Loyola Carrasco, "Study on the Level of Knowledge in Dental Medical Emergencies of Dentistry Students through Neutrosophic Values," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 90-107, 2020.
- [26] D. Coka Flores, J. R. Cadena Morillo, C. G. Rosero Martínez, and W. Ortiz Aguilar, "Selection of Experts to Validate a Research Proposal Using a Neutrosophic Method," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 71-80, 2020.
- [27] L. Wong Vázquez, Cueva Moncayo, María Fernanda., and L. P. Advendaño Castro, "Risk Factors Prioritization for Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 49-60, 2020.
- [28] J. M. Macías Bermúdez, G. K. Arreaga Farias, and L. Torres Torres, "Profiles of Human Trafficking Violence in Regions of Ecuador," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 200-207, 2020.
- [29] D. V. G. Mayorga, E. d. P. A. Escobar, and O. F. S. Montoya, "Neutrosophy Used to Measure the Legal and Socioeconomic Effect of Debtors," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 295-301, 2020.
- [30] C. R. Martínez, G. A. Hidalgo, M. A. Matos, and F. Smarandache, "Neutrosophy for Survey Analysis in Social Sciences," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 409-416, 2020.
- [31] P. A. M. Silva, A. R. Fernández, and L. A. G. Macías, "Neutrosophic Statistics to Analyze Prevalence of Dental Fluorosis," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 160-168, 2020.
- [32] P. A. Mena Silva, A. Romero Fernández, and L. A. Granda Macías, "Neutrosophic Statistics to Analyze Prevalence of Dental Fluorosis," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 160-168, 2020.
- [33] G. A. Gómez, J. F. G. García, S. D. Á. Gómez, and F. Smarandache, "Neutrosophic Sociogram for Group Analysis," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 417-427, 2020.
- [34] I. Pimienta Concepción, E. Mayorga Aldaz, L. Gabriel Flores, and E. González Caballero, "Neutrosophic Scale to Measure Psychopathic Personalities Based on Triple Refined Indeterminate Neutrosophic Sets," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 61-70, 2020.
- [35] A. J. P. Palacios, L. B. Bustamante, V. C. Armijo, and V. S. N. Luque, "Neutrosophic multicriteria method to evaluate the com-petencies of mayoral candidates," *Revista Asociación Latinoamericana de Ciencias Neutrosóficas. ISSN 2574-1101*, vol. 11, pp. 17-24, 2020.
- [36] N. V. Q. Arnaiz, N. G. Arias, and L. C. C. Muñoz, "Neutrosophic K-means Based Method for Handling Unlabeled Data," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 308-315, 2020.
- [37] P. E. D. P. Franco, A. J. P. Palacio, and I. A. C. Piza, "Neutrosophic Hypothesis to validate a Reform Project to Article 87 of the General Organic Code of Processes of Ecuador," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 316-322, 2020.
- [38] J. L. R. Villafuerte, L. D. T. Torres, and L. T. Jimenez, "Neutrosophic Hypothesis to validate a modification for Article 630 of the Integral Organic Criminal Code of Ecuador," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 260-266, 2020.
- [39] C. C. Guillot, D. R. M. Medina, and M. A. B. Ávalos, "Neutrosophic Evaluation of Depression Severity," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 242-249, 2020.
- [40] A. D. M. Manzano, J. Y. V. Villegas, L. M. O. Escobar, and L. T. Jiménez, "Neutrosophic Analysis of the Facultative Vote in the Electoral Process of Ecuador," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 355-360, 2020.
- [41] C. A. Escobar Suárez, R. Oliva Torres, and L. Espinoza Freire, "Neutrosophic Analysis of Complications Generated by Hypothyroidism during Pregnancy," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 141-150, 2020.
- [42] F. d. R. Lozada López, M. E. Villacreses Medina, and E. C. Villacis Lascano, "Measure of Knowledge in Students at Uniandes, Ecuador, on the Manifestations of Oral Cancer," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 151-159, 2020.
- [43] C. E. Ochoa Díaz, L. A. Colcha Ramos, M. J. Calderón Velásquez, and O. Pérez Peña, "Knowledge-based Hiring Recommender Model for Occasional Services in the Public Sector," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 176-183, 2020.
- [44] M. E. Á. Tapia, D. C. M. Raúl, and C. N. M. Vinicio, "Indeterminate Likert Scale for the Analysis of the Incidence of the Organic Administrative Code in the current Ecuadorian Legislation," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 329-335, 2020.
- [45] A. Abdel-Monem and A. Abdel Gawad, "A hybrid Model Using MCDM Methods and Bipolar Neutrosophic Sets for Select Optimal Wind Turbine: Case Study in Egypt," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 42, pp. 1-27, 2021.
- [46] A. S. Molina, W. A. C. Calle, and J. D. B. Remache, "The application of Microsoft Solution Framework Software Testing using Neutrosophic Numbers," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 267-276, 2020.
- [47] S. H. S. Al-Subhi, I. Pérez Pupo, R. García Vacacela, P. Y. Piñero Pérez, and M. Y. Leyva Vázquez, "A New Neutrosophic Cognitive Map with Neutrosophic Sets on Connections, Application in Project Management. ," *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 22. , pp. 63-75, 2018.
- [48] F. Smarandache, *An introduction to the Neutrosophic probability applied in quantum physics*: Infinite Study, 2000.
- [49] W. B. Vanantha, I. Kandasamy, and F. Smarandache, "Algebraic Structure of Neutrosophic Duplets in Neutrosophic Rings $\langle Z U I \rangle, \langle Q U I \rangle$ and $\langle R U I \rangle$." *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 23, pp. 85-95, 2018.
- [50] E. J. H. Antepara, *Competencies Interdependencies Analysis based on Neutrosophic Cognitive Mapping*: Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, 2017.
- [51] Pérez-Teruel, *Neutrosophic logic for mental model elicitation and analysis*.: Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, 2012.
- [52] F. Smarandache, *Neutrosophy, a new Branch of Philosophy*: Infinite Study, 2002.

- [53] W. V. Kandasamy and F. Smarandache, "Fuzzy Neutrosophic Models for Social Scientists.," *Education Publisher Inc.*, (2013)
- [54] F. Smarandache, "A Unifying Field in Logics: Neutrosophic Logic. Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Set, Neutrosophic Probability: Neutrosophic Logic. Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Set, Neutrosophic Probability: Infinite Study.," 2005.

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